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IZDRŽAVANA DECA OBVEZNIKA POREZA NA DOHODAK GRAĐANA

Zakon o porezu na dohodak građana Srbije prepoznaje maloletnu decu i usvojenike kao izdržavane članove porodice. U tu kategoriju spadaju još i deca, odnosno usvojenici na redovnom školovanju ili za vreme nezaposlenosti, ako sa obveznikom žive u domaćinstvu, i unuci, ako ih roditelji ne izdržavaju i ako žive u domaćinstvu sa obveznikom. U Srbiji se još uvek primenjuje mešoviti sistem poreza na dohodak građana, koji karakteriše dominacija cedularnog modela oporezivanja u odnosu na globalni ili sintetički. Karakteristika cedularnog modela je da se na iznos pojedinog prihoda plaćaju cedularni porezi koje karakteriše proporcionalna poreska stopa, i zanemarlivo mali broj poreskih olakšica koje prilagođavaju poresku obavezu porodičnom stanju obveznika. Na prvom mestu, predviđeno je da se primanja (osim naknade zarade), koja se ostvaruju u skladu sa zakonom kojim se uređuje finansijska podrška porodici sa decom, izuzimaju od oporezivanja. Zatim, predviđeno je i poresko oslobođenje za obveznika poreza na kapitalni dobitak koji sredstva od prodaje nepokretnosti uloži u rešavanje stambenog pitanja članova svoje porodice. Na kraju, maloletni članovi domaćinstva obveznika poreza na prihode od samostalne delatnosti oslobođeni su obaveze da svojom imovinom jemče za njegove obaveze. Fiskalni značaj ovih olakšica je veoma mali. Najvažnija olakšica date je u okviru godišnjeg poreza na dohodak građana, koji plaća mali broj lica. Za svakog izdržavanog član porodice, obveznik ostvaruje odbitak od 15% od prosečne zarade, s tim što je ukupan iznos odbitaka odgraničen. Poreska teorija je već dugi niz godina jednoglasna u stavu da je neophodno pristupiti radikalnoj reformi sistema poreza na dohodak građana. Novo rešenje bi moralo u većoj meri da uvaži porodične prilike obveznika, olakšavajući poresku obavezu u zavisnosti od broja dece koje obveznik izdržava.

Ključne reči: cedularni porezi, izdržavani članovi porodice, deca, porez na dohodak građana.

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DEPENDENT CHILDREN OF PERSONAL INCOME TAXPAYERS

The Personal Income Tax Act of the Republic of Serbia recognizes minor children and adoptees as dependants. This category also includes children or adoptees during their education or unemployment, if they live in the same household with the taxpayer, as well as grandchildren, if their parents do not support them and if they live in the household with the taxpayer. In Serbia, a mixed system of personal income tax is still applied, which is characterized by the dominance of the schedular model of taxation over the global or synthetic model. A characteristic of the schedular model is that a schedular tax is paid on the amount of each personal income, which is characterized by a proportional tax rate and a negligible number of tax reliefs that adjust the tax obligation based on the taxpayer's family situation. First of all, it is stipulated that the income (except for wage compensation) earned in accordance with the law regulating financial support for families with children is exempt from taxation. Furthermore, there is a tax exemption for the taxpayer on capital gains tax if the proceeds from the sale of real estate are invested in resolving the family members' housing issues. Finally, minor members of the household of the taxpayer who pays self-employment income tax are exempt from the obligation to guarantee for his obligations with their property. The fiscal significance of these reliefs is quite unsubstantial. The most important tax relief is provided within the annual personal income tax, which is paid by a small number of individuals. For each dependent family member, the taxpayer is entitled to a deduction of 15% of the average salary, with the total amount of deductions being capped. The tax law theory has long been unanimous in the view that a radical reform of the personal income tax system is necessary. The new solution should more substantially take into account the taxpayer's family circumstances and ease the tax obligation, depending on the number of children the taxpayer supports.

Keywords: schedular taxes, dependants, children, personal income tax.